

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

This article refers to the innovative ways of teaching English and making it available for most learner as well as the role of linguo-sociocultural comprehension in learning languages. The communicative approach in language teaching starts from a theory of language as communication. Communication is first of all exchanging opinions, information, notions of social, cultural, political and other aspects of everyday life. The world around us is the world of communication in various spheres. The modern communicative method represents a harmonious combination of many ways of teaching foreign languages, being, probably, at the top of the evolutionary pyramid of various educational methods. The main goal of language teaching is to develop learners' communicative competence. The adoption of a communicative approach raises important issues for teacher training, materials development, and testing 'and evaluation.

Key words: communicative approach, advantages, linguo-sociocultural way, innovative ways of teaching, critical way of thinking, creativity,.

In today's era, multilingualism has become more than just 'important'. Knowing a foreign language other than your native language has evolved to be extremely beneficial. Whether viewed from the financial or social aspect, being able to communicate in a foreign language helps to make 'real' connection with people and provides a better understanding of our language. Speaking a language gives a better understanding of the country's culture, gives an opportunity to interact with people more freely providing a greater scope of meeting new people, making new friends, more fun, and enjoyment. To achieve these goals foreign language learners should develop their communicative skills.

Another reason for learning a foreign language is that the knowledge of a foreign language enhances a cognitive and analytical abilities. Learning a foreign language is tough and involves a lot of mental exercise. On the individual level, it improves personality and increases a sense of self-worth. The need of language faculties has increased due to the -growing interest in students to learn foreign languages. The ability

to speak, read, write and understand more than one language is also remarkable and expands the liberties in life, especially for young people.

The importance of teaching and learning foreign languages is growing with every passing day and a foreign language is not just a subject but a tool for productive cross-cultural communication. Despite a perfect grammar knowledge and the years of study, our students may face difficulty expressing their meaning to native speakers. The problem that comes to light through is that grammar and lexical meanings of words alone cannot guarantee a person the ability to express themselves in a foreign language efficiently. By increasing our students' Communicative competence, we will enable them to interact successfully in a foreign language environment. Thus, teaching Communicative competence is the requirement of our modern life.

One of the elements of Communicative competence is Sociolinguistic competence that refers to the ability to use language that is appropriate to social contexts. Alptekin explains that social context refers to culture-specific contexts that include the norms, values, beliefs, and behavioural patterns of a culture [1]. For example, thanking a friend in a formal speech is different from how it is done over a meal.

Communication is an indispensable part of any community life in which people feel the need to interact with each other for certain reasons. It is through the concept of language that people can communicate with a number of interlocutors in a variety of settings. However, while interacting, people need to follow things beyond words. They need to know how to say something as well as when, where and to whom to say it.

Communicative language teaching makes use of real-life situations that necessitate communication. The teacher sets up a situation that students are likely to encounter in real life.. The real-life simulations change from day to day. Students' motivation to learn comes from their desire to communicate in meaningful ways about meaningful topics. The communicative approach could be said to be the product of educators and linguists who had grown dissatisfied with the audio-lingual and grammar-translation methods of foreign language instruction [4].

The sociocultural approach which now dominates the educational environment has among its strategic values the formation of cultural awareness, i.e. the idea worldview specific to the speaker of the foreign language..The essence of sociocultural approach is in teaching foreign languages as a means of cross-cultural communication and a way to understand foreign cultures and subcultures [5].

Communicative approach is an innovative way of teaching English and it is on the top of popularity rating among innovative approaches. It is aimed to practice communication. The communicative approach is based on the idea that learning language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When

learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language.

The world around us is the world of communication in various spheres. The modern communicative method represents a harmonious combination of many ways of teaching foreign languages, being, probably, at the top of the evolutionary pyramid of various educational methods. The communicative method develops all language skills — from oral and written speech to reading and listening. The goal is to teach a student to speak a foreign language not only freely, but also correctly.

To develop autonomous control of the target language for communication, language teachers must at all times allow students autonomy, and conversely discourage them from maintaining dependence. This can be done through provision of interactional activities with other students, either in person, through pair or group work to achieve the goal of effective communication in the target language [5]. Furthermore, small group work, goal or task-oriented group projects, and information gathering have been strongly advocated to increase meaningful interactions for the purpose of communication. It has been noted that student-centered interactional activities without teacher intervention, and spontaneous language use in authentic communication results in the unconscious development of the target language system [4].

The most obvious advantage in communicative language teaching is that of the increase of fluency in the target language. The approach also leads to gains in the areas of grammatical/sociolinguistic/discourse/strategic competence through communication. In order to do so, language teachers may restructure the traditional classroom environment to allow a variety of activities to take place simultaneously. Without being supported or assisted by the teacher, students may well be working with another or with other students: establishing social relations, seeking and giving information, expressing reactions, learning to do something, hiding intentions or talking their way out of trouble, persuading, discouraging, entertaining others, or displaying achievements

Literature

1. Alptekin, C. Towards intercultural communicative competence in ELT. – M., 2002. - 57-64 p.
2. Finocchiaro, M. & C. Brumfit. The Functional Notional Approach: From Theory to Practice.- New York: Oxford University Press , 1983.- 521p.
3. Littlewood, William. T. Communicative Language Teaching. - Cambridge University Press,2002. – 354 c.
4. Мадаминова Д. А. Communicative approaches of teaching foreign languages Молодой ученый. — 2016. — №9.5. — С. 63-65. — URL

5. Nunan, D. 1986. 'Communicative Language Teaching: The Learner's View.' Paper presented at the RELC Regional Seminar, - Singapore, 1986. - 21-25 p.
6. Сафонова В.В. Изучение языков межкультурного общения в контексте диалога культур и цивилизаций. – Воронеж: Истоки, 1996. – 184 с.
7. Тер-Минасова С. Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. – М : Слово, 2000. –264 с.